

Studies of the Kinetics Between Chromium Peroxydichromate and Various Acids. Part I. Sulphuric Acid

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The kinetics of the reaction between chromium peroxydichromate and sulphuric acid has been studied by Ostwald's isolation method. The total order of the reaction has been found to be 2 and its mechanism has also been suggested.

Pillai and Rai¹ have shown that the water decomposition product of blue peroxychromic acid, extracted with ethylacetate, is $\text{Cr}_2(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_8)_3$, *i.e.* chromium peroxydichromate, and have studied kinetics of the reaction of chromium peroxydichromate in sulphuric acid. In the present communication an attempt has been made to ascertain the total order of reaction between the two reactants by Ostwald's isolation method².

EXPERIMENTAL

The blue peroxychromic acid (now blue perchromate) was prepared and extracted with ethyl acetate (B.D.H., A.R.) as described earlier¹. This was carefully separated and washed with ice-cold distilled water. The blue perchromate was separated from the aqueous layer, taken into a Jena glass bottle, and kept in a refrigerator. The blue solution (100 ml) was withdrawn in a flask containing distilled water (30 ml) and kept for decomposition at a cold place. When the ethyl acetate layer became colorless, the aqueous layer was separated carefully. This was then diluted and the experiment was started within half an hour of this dilution to avoid hydrolysis of the per-salt.

Two Erlenmeyer flasks (250 ml) were taken containing 50 ml each of water decomposition product and $2N\text{-H}_2\text{SO}_4$, respectively. The strength of chromium peroxydichromate was kept $N/20$, titrating iodometrically against a standard thiosulphate solution. The flasks were kept in a thermostat below 50° . After about 20 min., when the contents of the flasks attained the temperature of the thermostat, 25 ml of each solution was mixed in a third flask, previously kept in the thermostat, and stop-watch was started when half of the solution was added. An aliquot the reaction mixture (5 ml) was withdrawn after a definite interval of time in a beaker having potassium iodide solution and the liberated iodine was titrated iodometrically against the same sodium thiosulphate solution. The same experiments were repeated with $1N\text{-H}_2\text{SO}_4$ under the same experimental conditions.

1. *This Journal*, 1963, **40**, 343; 1964, **41**, 217.

2. Dhar, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, **111**, 707.

Order of Reaction.—The rate of the chemical reaction may be expressed by the equation:

$$-dc_1/dt = k c_1^m c_2^n \quad \dots \quad (i)$$

where c_1 and c_2 represent concentrations of chromium peroxydichromate and sulphuric acid, respectively, and k is the velocity constant or specific rate constant, which is given by:

$$k = k^0 e^{-E/RT} \quad \dots \quad (ii)$$

where k^0 is the non-exponential term in the Arrhenius equation, E is the Arrhenius activation energy in cal. mole⁻¹, R is a gas constant expressed in mole⁻¹ degree⁻¹, and T is the absolute temperature.

Determination of m.—In the following series of experiments, the sulphuric acid was used in large excess and hence the concentration of the sulphuric acid might be taken practically constant during the course of the reaction. Thus the rate equation (i) takes the form:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{where} \quad -dc_1/dt &= k(c_2)^n c_1^m = k_1 c_1^m & \dots & \dots & (iii) \\ & k_1 = k c_2^n & \dots & \dots & (iv) \end{aligned}$$

The order of the reaction under the conditions specified is therefore the same as m .

Since the free chromium peroxydichromate in solution is equivalent to the amount of sodium thiosulphate required, the observations are therefore expressed by the volume of sodium thiosulphate in ml. The results of the experiments are recorded in the following tables.

TABLE I

Chromium peroxydichromate = 25 ml. H₂SO₄ = 25 ml. Temp. = 20°.

Reaction mixture withdrawn each time = 5 ml.

Time.	(a-x) _t	k = 1/t. log a/(a-x).	Time.	(a-x) _t	k = 1/t. log a/(a-x).
	A. With 2N-H ₂ SO ₄ .			B. With 1N-H ₂ SO ₄ .	
0.0 min.	11.25 ml	..	0.0 min.	11.25 ml	..
10.5	11.05	0.0007413	16.0	11.15	0.0003062
24.5	10.80	0.0007224	40.5	10.95	0.0002889
45.0	10.45	0.0007111	70.0	10.70	0.0003093
65.0	10.05	0.0007539	100.0	10.55	0.0002790
88.5	9.60	0.0007762	129.5	10.30	0.0002957
110.5	9.15	0.0007925	159.5	15.15	0.0002802
		Mean 0.0007498			Mean 0.0002932

TABLE II

Temp. = 25°. Other conditions same as in Table I.

Time.	(a-x).	$k=1/t. \log a/(a-x).$	Time.	(a-x).	$k=1/t. \log a/(a-x).$
A. With 2N-H ₂ SO ₄ .			B. With 1N-H ₂ SO ₄ .		
0.0 min.	11.25 ml	..	0.0 min.	11.25 ml	..
9.5	10.15	0.004826	10.5	10.70	0.002066
18.0	9.35	0.004459	25.0	10.10	0.001915
30.0	8.15	0.004665	40.0	9.60	0.001720
40.0	7.20	0.004840	55.0	9.00	0.001762
52.5	6.30	0.004795	70.0	8.50	0.001739
62.5	5.55	0.004801	85.0	8.00	0.001746
		Mean 0.004731			Mean 0.001825

TABLE III

Temp. = 35°. Other conditions same as in Table I.

Time.	(a-x).	$k=1/t. \log a/(a-x).$	Time.	(a-x).	$k=1/t. \log a/(a-x).$
A. With 2N-H ₂ SO ₄			B. With 1N-H ₂ SO ₄ .		
0.0 min.	11.25 ml	..	0.0 min.	11.25 ml	..
8.5	9.50	0.008634	9.0	10.45	0.003555
18.5	7.95	0.008134	17.0	9.80	0.003524
27.0	6.55	0.008696	27.0	9.10	0.003413
36.0	5.40	0.008774	34.0	8.55	0.003452
43.5	4.80	0.008710	43.0	7.90	0.003580
53.0	3.90	0.008680	54.0	7.25	0.003530
		Mean 0.008605			Mean 0.003509

DISCUSSION

It is quite clear from the tables that the values of velocity constant (k) are fairly constant for the unimolecular reaction and thus the value of m , i.e. order with respect to chromium peroxydichromate, will be 1.

In Ostwald's isolation method used, constant k is dependent on the concentration of H₂SO₄ by the equation :

$$k_1 = kc_1^n$$

where c_1 is the concentration of H₂SO₄ and n is the number of its molecules taking part in the reaction.

From Table I, if the values of the velocity constants are k^I , and k^{II} , when the con-

concentrations of H_2SO_4 are $2N$ and $1N$, respectively, and the concentration of the chromium peroxydichromate is same in both the cases, is,

$$k_1^I = k \cdot 2.0^n \quad \text{and} \quad k_1^{II} = k \cdot 1.0^n$$

so

$$n = \frac{\log k_1^I}{\log k_1^{II}} / \log 2/1$$

so,

$$n = \frac{\log k_1^I}{\log k_1^{II}} / \log 2$$

By substituting the values recorded in Table I in the above relation, the values of n come out to be 1.342, 1.322, 1.198, 1.434, 1.394, and 1.535. If the values of k_1^I and k_1^{II} in Table II are substituted, the values of n come out to be 1.224, 1.220, 1.440, 1.452, 1.462, and 1.460. When values of k_1^I and k_1^{II} in Table III are substituted, values of n come out to be 1.280, 1.235, 1.350, 1.346, 1.284, and 1.298.

From the above values of n , it is clear that the order of the reaction, n , is 1 and therefore the total order of reaction, *i.e.* $m+n$, will be 2 in the case of chromium peroxydichromate and sulphuric acid.

The second order of reaction between the two reactants, *viz.*, chromium peroxydichromate and sulphuric acid, may be explained in the following manner:

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